

PATRIARCHAL MENTALITY: A STUDY OF DISTRICT SWAT

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Abstract

This research study deals with the negative consequences of patriarchal social structure in district Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, Pakistan. The main objective of this research paper is to find out the potentials associated with a patriarchal society. The research paradigm which is used in this study is interpretivism, and the research was carried out on qualitative research methodology. The researcher used qualitative research methodology in order to find out the negative and harmful consequences of patriarchal social structure i.e. gender based violence and discrimination, inequality in resource distribution, ignorance in decision – making process of the household, and lack of basic education of women. Patriarchy is not only a structure of society which affects the lives of women but it is also a belief system which gives authority to men which affects social development and prosperity of women. The data was collected from both genders (mostly from women) regarding patriarchy. The data collection tools used in this research were in-depth interviews, and observation. The collected data was then analyzed through thematic analysis and finally, the conclusion which has drawn from the analysis and interpretation of data states that patriarchal social structure is responsible for gender-based violence, gender discrimination and inequality and domestic violence. The prevailing social set up (Patriarchy) affects the lives of all women across the world, but after reaching to the conclusion of this research, the researcher pointed out that in swat society male domination is really a barrier block to the development and prosperity of women.

INTRODUCTION

Patriarchy is a systematic social structure of society that institutionalizes male physical, social, cultural and economic power over women. Patriarchal mentality refers to a hegemonic power of men over their women (Connel, 2005). Patriarchy refers to the structure of society where there is male dominancy. The rule of the father or patriarch over their family is termed as patriarchy. Patriarchal social structure prevails in every society and country all over the world. Due to patriarchal

social structure women are systematically deprived of their basic needs, and they have the lack of decision – making process of the family. In such societies women have no chance to participate in opportunities through which they can live a standard life. In most of the societies every decision is taken by man who considers himself the dominant one, while woman, have not given any power to participate in decision – making process of the family and she is considered the sub

- missive. Women are subject to discrimination and they also experiencing oppression based on their gender. In the world, a culture existed which is totally against women (Kandiyoti 1988), that create oppression for women on both sides, on one side they exploited in the family and on another side, they face discrimination in a labour market.

The purpose of this paper is to explore those problems caused by patriarchal social structure in Swat society. Pakistan is one of those countries where the structure of the society is a patriarchal one, and the problems which are associated with patriarchy, are also exist in Pakistani society. This study was conducted in district Swat, province Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. In swat, most of the people are known as 'Pathan' or 'Pakhtoon' and or 'Pashtoon'. Pashtoon have their own way of life and they following a unique feature of their own known as 'Pashtunwali'. In Pashtunwali, they have their own principles and rules with accordance they live their lives (Thomas H. Johnson and M. Chris Mason, 2008). In Swat society, patriarchal social structure also exists, and due to this structure, the male members of the society do not allow women to take part in daily base activities. Due to the prevalence of male dominancy in Swat society, women did not have any access to opportunity of job, health care, family planning, higher education and basic education as well, selection of spouse, decision - making processes of the family, and many more hurdles are facing to women in Swat society. In patriarchal society, men use their own power to control all aspects of the women's life included; access to education, health care, business opportunities, and selection of life partner. In a male dominated society, women have not given such opportunities to go outside from home for a job or any other activity. It means that they are bounded to 'Chadar and Chaardiwari', which means they should be subjected to the familial services. The familial services (domesticity) included; care of husband and children in a family. Further, women did not have any extra time to participate in income earning opportunities outside home (Khattak, 2002; Ali et al., 2010).

1. Review of Literature

In a patriarchal society, men hold all the areas of women life like, education, health care, family planning, and income earning opportunities. In patriarchal society, women are treated to be only performing the familial services, and they are restricted to the cultural values and beliefs (Chadar and Chaardiwari). It means that male member of the family did not support nor allow their women to go outside home (Khattak, 2002; Ali et al., 2010). According to Walby (1990), patriarchy is a system of societal structure in which the male members of the family dominate, oppress, and exploit women. Walby further explains that in a male dominated society, there are some cultural and traditional values which are not in the favor of women. The male members of the family kept their women suppressed. Women are not able to raise a voice for their basic rights because of the oppressive patriarchy which reign in every society (Ibid). A social system, which exploits and control women's education, women's reproduction, women's job opportunities, women's sexuality, women's access to outside activities are under the control of male or patriarchate (Walby, 1990). Furthermore, Walby said that, patriarchy took shape through six interrelated structures i.e. production relation in the household, paid work, patriarchal state, male violence, patriarchal relation in sexuality, and patriarchal cultural institutions. He also argues that there are two forms of patriarchy i.e. private and public patriarchy. According to him, private patriarchy refers to gender relation in the family in which men oppress and exploit their women. While on the other side, public patriarchy is so much related to public world. Walby states that in the public sphere women are totally separated from power and wealth.

There are two types of patriarchy i.e. public and private. In private patriarchy women are not able to do something without the decision of the male members. In this type of patriarchy women are live their lives under the control of the head of the family. When the entire family is under the control of men, then there is no permission to women to go schools and get the basic education. While public patriarchy on the other hand, related

to the public spaces. It means that exploitation of women out of the family. Women are being subjected to exploitation out of the family like in education, paid work, and other outdoor opportunities (Alabi et al. 2013).

According to Heath and Ciscel (1988), in a patriarchal society, power and authority are in the hand of the male members of the family, they control and holds the entries' family activities included both paid work and non - work. Hartmann (1981) argued that there is a link between patriarchy and capitalism. In the capitalistic and patriarchal structure of the economy male and female relation is based on material. In the materialistic structure of the economy men control and subjugate women's work power. Additionally, In the patriarchal nature of politics men used to exercise their power and authority while exclude women from such political spheres (Rosaldo 1974).

Hartman (1981) states that the two exploitation sites of women are the market place and the family, it means that women are exploited in the family and also in the market place. The male members of the society look for high - status job and they achieve it by constant struggle while women remain in low - status job. Why because the gender relation is so much biased toward women in a patriarchal market and patriarchal family. Inside the family, women perform more work than men and they have no access to the outside work. In a male dominated society, women are only subject to the familial services, and the male member denied such amenities of women in the market place. This deprivation of women increases with the passage of time and resulted more vulnerability of women in marriage arrangements, paid work panning, and other achievements. According to Lim (1997), patriarchy is a system where male members of the society are considered as the dominant one who enjoys all the amenities of life, while women are considered as the subordinate one who remain dependent on men. It means that the gender relation is unequal in every society, culture, and economy. He further argued that the inferiority and the lower rank of the women in a capitalistic

society is the result of the prevalence patriarchal social structure and social relations.

Women, all over the world, are not only experiencing biological discrimination but also, they are suffering psychologically due to patriarchy. Modern psychologists argued that due to patriarchal social structure women of all societies are subject to biological oppression. This biological oppression with the passage of time determines some psychological and mental issues to women. It means that women are deprived from their basic biological needs and rights which resulted psychological and mental illness to women. In simple words, the more the social system is appreciable to women, the more women will be psychologically comfortable (Freud 1977). Additionally, according to Zahidie & Jamali (2013), in South Asian countries gender disparity is a responsible factor behind women's anxiety and depression. Similarly, in a male dominated countries gender inequality is a main cause of women's suicide (Qasim 2015). Harassment and discrimination of women are responsible for stress, anxiety, and depression of women (McDonald et al., 2021).

According to Daily Dawn (2011) report gender - based violence and women subordination are the result of the patriarchal culture of the country. Some research studies shows that women in Pakistan are suffering from sexual harassment, domestic violence, dowry death, early pregnancy, tuberculosis and osteoporosis (Nasar 2012). Furthermore, Pakistan is one of the patriarchal countries where women have no access to education, health care decision - making processes of the household etc.

This research study was conducted in district Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, Pakistan. The aim of this research paper was to explore the issues of patriarchal social structure to women life. Swat is also a patriarchal society where women face lots of issues in their lives. In a male dominated society, women have the lack of such opportunities included; education, health care, the right to vote, the right to contest election, the right to access public spaces, the right to select spouse for herself and many more. Swat is also one of those societies where the above-mentioned problems are facing to

women. The existence of these problems attracted the researcher to conduct a research study on patriarchal mentality in district Swat.

2. Methodology

Literally methodology means the study of method. In research, it can be defined as those methods and techniques which are used for investigating a problem. In social sciences, there are three major methodologies i.e. qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods research (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2006). These methodologies are used for specific research area depending upon the nature of the problem. In this reaserch study the reasecher used qualitative research method because it was more suitable to deeply understands patriarchal mentality. The researcher has used qualitataive research method for exploring patriarchal mentality in district Swat. Creating a detailed and comprehensive account of your observations as a researcher is the goal of qualitative research methodology (Macdonald et al., 2008). Data collection is a major and very important step in a research process which involve colleting information from the respondents regarding the issue. The researcher have collected data through indepth interviews from 16 participants. Researchers often struggles with determining the appropriate size of their sample, which is a crucial decision in research design. In qualitative research the number of samples are very low because it is a subjective study and focusing on the achievment of deep information about the research problem. According to Cochran, (1977) an overly large sample can result in unnecessary resource expenditure, whereas a sample that is too small may yield results that lack reliability and practical significance. According to Guest (2006) for homogeneous qualitative studies using purposeful sampling, a sample size of 12 participants is often sufficient to achieve data saturation, where the data collected becomes redundant and no further insights are gained. According to Creswell (2014), when there is a range of sample size from 5 - 25 participants the study will be more authentic and relibale. In this research study the researcher collected data from 16 participants which comes under the range of 05

to 25 sample size given by Creswell. Furthermore, the collected data was analyzed through thematic analysis and reached to a meaningful conclusion.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. The Impact of Patriarchy on Women in Family Set up.

In many patriarchal societies, family is considered the starting point of discrimination and oppression for women. It means that gender violence, gender inequality, gender sexual abuse and many other gender related problems starts from the household and then spread to the entire society. According to Heath and Ciscel (1988), in a patriarchal society, power and authority are in the hand of the male members of the family, they control and holds the entries' family activities included both paid work and non - work. In simple words, it means that, family, in a patriarchal society, is under the control of male members. In this regard, a participant in the study said;

“Gender - based violence and exploitation of women took shape from the family. In our society, there is no place for women due to the reign of patriarchal culture. The head of the family/father support their boy's children while female babies are still neglecting in our society. In this society (Swat), when a male baby is born it consider the matter of status, means the family feels honor, while if a girl baby is born, she is considered a burden on the family. The patriarch in the Swat society shows sadness and negative feelings on the birth of the girl baby. Further, the decision - making of the family is only in the favor of the male members. In Swat society, we are being deprived from basic education, the right to inheritance, the right to hold public places, the right to take part in the family arrangements, the right to select a life partner for herself, the right to basic socialization by family. These all challenges are associated to women in our society. She further states that if the family is not against to the right of the women, and if the family is a supportive unit for women, so the outside world will not be able to discourage women development and prosperity in the region”

On the basis of the above-mentioned participant views, it is clear that family is the primary unit of women exploitation. In a male dominated society, family is an oppressive unit for women exploitation. The gender division of labor is unequal in the family. Resource distributions of the household are unequal in Swat society. It means that high privileges and resources are in the hand of the male members of the society and women are deprived from such resources. The male members look for, and achieve the standard education while women haven't such opportunities of even basic education. In Swat, women are deprived from their inheritance rights. The parents and elder brothers denied the right to inherit of their women. This deprivation of women increases with the passage of time which result a huge impact on women's life and they remain dependent on their men for each and every thing. Furthermore, due to gender blindness the women haven't a right to choose a life partner for herself. In simple words, women are exploited from their birth till death in a patriarchal family. According to Friedrich Engels (1884/1902), family is like a class in which men oppressing women. It is clear that women are being surrender to patriarchal social structure. A participant says: "In Swat society women are surrender to their men because the social structure of the family is much related to men and they control each and everything. The biological composition of women is so much weak and they are not able to perform a work like men. A man's working ability is comparatively higher than that of women ability. The male member performs all the things for their child and wives. Women are subjected to their men's decision just because of male superiority"

In the views of the participant, patriarchal social structure is not a god gifted one. Exploitation and oppression on the basis of gender and sex are the result of the biological construction of women. It is reality that women are biologically so weak and they cannot perform those activities which men can do. Moreover, Allah SWT created women with soft and weak bodily features. Due to this weakness and softness, they are not able to do hard work like men. So, women are surrender to

patriarchal social structure due to their feminine ideology and weak biological composition.

3.2. Patriarchy and Women Paid work

Women income earning opportunity is also a considerable point of discussion because in a male dominated society women did not have such opportunity to get a job or join a business sector. The patriarchal structure of society is such a structure which goes is totally related to the ideology of capitalism. The structure of the economy is a capitalistic one in which one group (male) enjoys high - status job with the expenses of the other group (female). The male members in paid work kept their women in oppression. The two things are very much responsible for the oppression and exploitation of women in paid work i.e. the structure of the economy (capitalism) and the structure of the family (patriarchy). Hartmann (1981) argued that there is a link between patriarchy and capitalism. In the capitalistic and patriarchal structure of the economy male and female relation is based on material. In the materialistic structure of the economy men control and subjugate women's work power. A participant in the study said:

"Due to male supremacy and power, we (women) are facing difficult and stern problems in job or any other economic related activities. We also have the right to earn for herself in order to live a standard life. But male members of the region (Swat) aren't in the favor of this who actually want to earn and survive their family by their own. the women in paid work have some difficult issues in the region. The first thing is the lack of the permission of the male members who not allow their women to go for a job and earn money. Secondly, when the women go for outside job, they face wage rate discrimination and exploitation in the capitalistic economic market. In some competitive labor market women are subjected to the policy of quid - pro - quo. The quid - pro - quo situation created where women usually surrender or they are subjected to unwanted demands which are totally immoral"

The participant actually views patriarchy as a barrier block to women development and prosperity. In such societies women are working in

the factories or other organizations and whatever income they produce are so less to meet their basic needs. Issues related to income are mostly founded in the developing and backward countries. Pakistan is also one of those countries where the unequal economic relation is reign between male and female. In Swat society women are deprived from their economic earning opportunities where male members of the family not allow their women to cross the limit of the culture (Chadar and Chaardiwari). The father or patriarchate approached their women to be live inside Chaardiwari of the home. So, the first thing is the lack of the family permission to women or girls for a job and the second thing is the oppressive structure of the economic market. In the economic market male members control all the economic activities and they exploit and suppress the women. In simple words, the gender relation is unequal in economic sector of the Swat society.

3.3. Patriarchy and Women Political Participation

In the political context, women are being deprived from their political rights. Discrimination on the basis of gender in politics is globally a topic of discussion. The women deprivation of the political rights is the result of the patriarchal nature of politics. Women in the world are excluded from political arena. In the patriarchal nature of politics men used to exercise their power and authority to exclude women from such political power and authority (Rosaldo 1974). According to UN Statistics 2019, 70% of men occupied the seats in parliament all over the world. Due to some gender role ideologies women are only subjected to daily chores of the household (Bari 2005). From the above point of views of researchers, it is clear that women are globally excluded from political rights.

In this regard a participant in the study said:

“The male members of the family do not support nor allow women participation in politics. Basically, the people of the Swat society are more reliable on their traditional and religious beliefs and principles. In simple words, they are following their religious beliefs through which they do not allow their women to take part in politics. Secondly, their cultural values are so valuable to

them. They want their women in Purdah (veil). Another important thing is male supremacy, and it means that the male members of the family do not allow their women to politics. In patriarchal society men afraid of women leadership, they do not want their women to become a leader”

In Swat, women are deprived from their political participation. The researcher observed some reasons in the interviews i.e. patriarchal nature of politics, religious and cultural beliefs and principles, men fear of the women’s leadership etc. these reasons are very much responsible for women deprivation of the political rights. Additionally, the right to vote and the right to contest election are the basic rights for every citizen. But unfortunately, women in the Swat society have been deprived from such rights. In a patriarchal society, the political system is male – centered and male – identified, where men can only participate. The participation of men in politics is responsible for the exclusion of women participation in politics due to the patriarchal nature of politics.

3.4. Patriarchy and Women’s Mental Health

Patriarchal social structure is not only responsible for social issues related to women, but it also affects the mental and psychological health of women as well. In patriarchal societies women are excluded from many social events. There is no right for women to raise voice for herself in such societies. When the male members kept their women in a subordinate position the women become more vulnerable and dependent on men. With the passage of time this vulnerability and dependency of women by their men increases which result a huge impact on women’s mental health. According to Zahidie & Jamali (2013), in South Asian countries gender disparity is a responsible factor behind women’s anxiety and depression. Similarly, in a male dominated countries gender inequality is a main cause of women’s suicide (Qasim 2015). Participants in the study states their arguments that are:

“In Swat, patriarchy is basically a barrier block to women development and prosperity. All the decisions of the family are going on male choice. The male members usually control women all over

the world. The women participation and going out of home for any activity is basically considered stigma and shame by their men. So, in Swat we (women) are continuously dependent on men in each and every walk of life. This consistency of male supremacy on women increases with the passage of time which result a huge impact on our mental health. We (women) are also human being, and we have the right to education, paid work, participation in decision - making process of the family, selection of life partner. But unfortunately, men do not allow women participation in any walk of life. They (men) actually keep their women suppress due to the oppressive social structure of patriarchy. Due to this suppressive and subordinate position of women they face anxiety, depression and other psychological illness. We (women) sometimes want to finish our life and to do suicide”

In the participants views, patriarchal social structure is a barrier block to women development. Women, all over the world have the need to earn income and participate in every decision of the household. But due to the reign of patriarchy in Swat, women are deprived from such activities. In a patriarchal society, women are subjected to all kinds of discrimination and oppression both in the family and outside the family. Firstly, in the family set up women are being impacting due to the harsh behave of the male members. Further, women in the family are under the control of women and they do not go out of home without the permission of men. Secondly, women are also facing discrimination and oppression outside home like in education, health sector, voting, economic market etc. In patriarchal societies, women are working in the same fields like men often face discrimination and harassment. This harassment and discrimination of women are responsible for stress, anxiety, and depression of women (McDonald et al., 2021). Additionally, women in Swat, have no right to participate in the household's decision because male members do not allow their participation. In a patriarchal society (Swat) women have placed in a very worse situation. In simple words, patriarchy is responsible for women's mental health in district Swat.

3.5. Patriarchy and Women's Education

Patriarchy and women education is a considerable topic of discussion all over the world. Women in district Swat are deprived from basic education. It is a reality that a man can empower another man, but for women, who can empower the entire family. The women members of the family can change and socialize all members of the family by providing them home - based knowledge and also school-based knowledge. But due to the prevalence of patriarchal culture in district Swat women are totally excluded from educational right because patriarchy is a male - identified and male - centered culture that all time focuses on, and support the male members of the society. According to Alabi and colleagues (2013), due to the oppressive patriarchal structure of the society female education is not so valued like men. A culture is prevailed in each and every society in which male dominate women in every walk of life. The education institutions in such societies are in the favor of the male members. There are two types of patriarchy i.e. public and private. In private patriarchy women are not able to do something without the decision of the male members. In this type of patriarchy women are live their lives under the control of the head of the family. When the entire family is under the control of men, then there is no permission to women to go schools and get the basic education. While public patriarchy on the other hand, related to the public spaces. It means that exploitation of women out of the family. Women are being subjected to exploitation out of the family like in education, paid work, and other outdoor opportunities (Alabi et al. 2013). In a male dominated society women are deprived from their basic education. Swat is also one of those societies where the status of women's education is totally ignored. A participant said:

“In this society (Swat), I observed that women education is placed in very low rank. The first thing which is highly affecting women education in Swat is the supremacy of the male members of the family. The male members of the family approached that women will only perform the household activities. My father and elder brothers did not allow me to get higher education; they

usually thought that women education in district Swat is not much secure. When I passed my 8th class examination, they prohibited me that not to go to school anymore. The people of Swat society are Pashtoon who following their cultural values very strictly, and they want their women in Purdah (veil). The male members in Swat think of women that they are only made for marriage, and they will be producing children. Most illiterate people in Swat consider their women as a sexual machine. Additionally, another barrier block to women education is the belief of the people that the lack of female teachers in the education institutions. They think that how can I send my daughter or sister to schools where there are no female teachers. Similarly, co-education is also a problem to women education, because unfortunately in Swat separate schools, colleges and universities for girls are very scarce and limited. Finally, men support the education of boys and prohibit women education in Swat. This prohibition of women education by their men is a patriarchal belief and a negative impact of patriarchy to women development and prosperity”

The participant emphasizes the negative impacts of patriarchy on women education in district Swat. Analyzing primary and secondary data we can say that education is necessary both for male and female. But due to the existing patriarchal social structure women education are ignored in every society. It is reality that if you educate a man, you educate a man, but if you educate a woman, you educate a nation. Women education is so much important because it will bring positive change in the family as well as in the society. The two things were discussed in the above passage which are responsible for women education i.e. ‘the family’ and ‘the education institutions. In the family set up women are subjected to the decisions of male members. Whatever the male members want the women will do that irrespective of their own choice. In a male dominated society men do not favor nor allow women education. They live their lives according to the culture which they have. In case of Swat, most of the peoples are Pashtoon who are following the cultural beliefs of Chadar and Chaardiwari. Additionally, the structure of education is also a patriarchal one. It means that

education is male – identified and male – centered. All people support the education of male and not of female. So, the family structure in Swat is a patriarchal one regarding education in which there exist the support of the male’s education and negligence of the female education. Discrimination in gender education starts from the family and then spread to education institutions. Secondly, the first problem is the lack of separate schools, colleges, and universities for women in district Swat. The lack of female teachers is also a big issue to women education. It is a ridiculous point that a person did not allow their girls to schools but always asking for female teacher and female physician. In education institutions, women are exploiting because it is male – centered. In most of the education institutions teachers are male who also have the belief of patriarchy that support male students and neglect female students. In simple words, female students are exploiting in schools, colleges and universities. In higher education female students are sometimes asking for immoral demands when they ask for their rights. It means that women are subjected to any form of discrimination and exploitation in education institutions.

4. Conclusion

The researcher reached to conclusion that patriarchal social structure greatly affects women lives in district Swat. It is examined in the study that there are lots of hurdles to women due to the reign of patriarchal social structure. The researcher used qualitative research methodology for this research paper in order to explore the impacts of patriarchal mentality. The researcher utilized in – depth interview and then analyzed the data through thematic analysis for the findings of the research problem. Finally, conclusion states that patriarchy is a barrier block to women development and prosperity. It is cleared that due to the existence of patriarchy in district swat women are deprived from their basic rights included: education, health care, family planning, selection of spouse, decision – making processes of the family, income earning opportunities etc. Moreover, women participation in politics like the right to vote and the right to contest election are

also neglecting in Swat society. Study also showed that when there are no equal rights for women, they may face mental and psychological illness. Simply we can say that patriarchy is like a barrier block to women development and prosperity.

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